

June
2020

IReL Survey Report: Article Processing Charges

DR CATHERINE FERRIS
IReL Open Scholarship Officer

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report comprises the results of the [IReL](#) article processing charges (APC) survey, distributed to member researchers during a two-month period in late 2019. The survey data on which this report is based accompanies the report in unredacted form (the survey was purposefully anonymous at capture).¹

The report examines responses from 848 researchers from Dublin City University, Maynooth University, National University of Ireland Galway, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Trinity College Dublin, Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin), University College Cork, University College Dublin and University of Limerick. The participants were queried on whether they had published open access (OA) journal articles, paid APCs, how much they had paid and how they had paid those charges. To provide comparative data, researchers were also asked about other publishing charges and how these were funded.

The results of this survey show that close to €1.4 million in APCs were paid by IReL researchers for publication of their last three OA articles. This demonstrates the current publishing environment for Irish researchers and gives context for IReL negotiations. Most striking from the data is that 20% of APCs were paid from the researcher's personal funds. This contravenes best practice for OA charges (where they apply) but demonstrates a lack of dedicated infrastructural support. This figure provides a baseline for IReL to target, for the elimination of the need for personal funding, through OA agreements. The results of the survey also show that 36% of APCs were funded from external grants. As IReL moves to potentially support all members' publishing through OA agreements, this figure helps to inform IReL's future funding model(s).

INTRODUCTION

In July 2019, IReL published their [principles for Open Access publisher agreements](#), based on the [LIBER principles](#).² Under 'Licensing and Open Access go Hand-in-Hand', the principles state:

Increased spending on APCs should result in proportionately lower spending on subscription fees.

This is in line with the Max Planck Digital Library white paper 'Disrupting the subscription journals' business model for the necessary large-scale transformation to open access'³ which concluded:

¹ Catherine Ferris, *IReL Survey Data: Article Processing Charges* (19 June 2020), [10.5281/zenodo.3891033](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3891033)

² "IReL Principles for Open Access Publisher Agreements from 2020," IReL, accessed May 20, 2020, <https://irel.ie/irel-principles-for-open-access-publisher-agreements-from-2020/>; "Open Access: Five Principles for Negotiations with Publishers," LIBER Europe, accessed May 20, 2020, <https://libereurope.eu/blog/2017/09/07/open-access-five-principles-for-negotiations-with-publishers/>

³ Ralf Schimmer, Kai Karin Geschuhn, Andreas Vogler, *Disrupting the Subscription Journals' Business Model for the Necessary Large-Scale Transformation to Open Access: A Max Planck Digital Library Open Access Policy White Paper* (2015), 7, accessed May 20, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.17617/1.3>

There is currently already enough money in the system. A large-scale transformation from subscription to open access publishing is possible without added expense.

IReL, based in Maynooth University, is a consortium responsible for e-resource licensing for participating Irish higher education institutions and the provision of administrative, technical and community support for the Irish ORCID consortium. In August 2019, the new post of IReL Open Scholarship Officer was created to manage the national ORCID consortium and support IReL's OA publisher negotiations by collating and analysing publication data. This latter work will result in a detailed dataset of IReL members' corresponding author publishing output, by publisher, categorized according to open access status, with item-level APC data where available.

In the interim, and to support the work of IReL in negotiating OA deals with publishers, this survey was launched in October 2019. The goals of the survey were to determine the extent of APC payments within the IReL research community, to ascertain the levels of APC payments by authors from IReL member institutions and to query the proportion of money currently being paid for OA publishing from personal, institutional and grant funding. It furthermore sought to enable comparison of those funding sources with funding for non-OA publishing.

Seven IReL member institutions have implemented APC tracking within their financial and administrative systems to provide data on annual APC spend from institutional funds. However, institutions are only one component of the funding landscape. Through analysis of the survey, this report seeks to provide the IReL consortium with a high-level representation of the current state of OA funding to clarify (a) the extent to which personal funds are being used and therefore the level of urgency of which national OA agreements are needed and (b) the extent of grant funding currently being used, which are likely move to transition to IReL's agreements, and could challenge IReL's capacity for funding OA agreements.

METHODOLOGY

This research was carried out by survey, utilising questions based on the University of California Libraries' ['Pay It Forward' Report](#) Author Survey Instrument (2016).⁴ That survey was developed by a research team, assisted by the project's principal investigator, economic modelling team and focus groups with iterative development, testing and piloting for language and logic.⁵ A subsection of this survey content was employed

⁴ University of California Libraries, *Pay It Forward: Investigating a Sustainable Model of Open Access Article Processing Charges for Large North American Research Institutions* | Mellon Foundation (2016), accessed May 20, 2020, <https://www.library.ucdavis.edu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/ICIS-UC-Pay-It-Forward-Final-Report.rev..7.18.16.pdf>

⁵ University of California Libraries, *Pay It Forward*, 23

for IReL purposes, focusing on APC payments only (see Appendix 1). Minor changes were made to the language in three instances:

- Question 2, ‘What is your home institution’ was added to facilitate analysis by institution.
- Question 3, ‘Have you ever published in an open access journal’ was changed to ‘Have you ever published an open access journal article?’ to clarify and ensure the survey captured both hybrid and gold publications.
- Questions 6 through 8, ‘How much (in US dollars) was paid for the APCs of your most recent articles’ were changed to ‘How much (in Euro) was paid for the APCs of your most recent articles?’ to reflect the IReL member audience.

Existing survey text was utilised for time efficiency but also to assert the impartiality of the surveyor on the topic. This approach brought limitations, particularly (a) in the lack of time-frame data in the survey questions, thereby inhibiting benchmarking of the survey results against other national annual figures (b) in the structure of the survey, which prevents the mapping of specific payments to their funding sources.

The IReL survey was developed and distributed using Microsoft Forms software, hosted on the IReL Open Scholarship Officer’s Maynooth University Office365 ProPlus account. An ethical and GDPR statement was provided and informed consent was obtained through a compulsory drop down (yes/no). If consent was not provided, the survey concluded immediately. As GDPR and anonymity was of a primary consideration in the construction of the survey, no personally identifiable information was captured.

The survey was sent to the IReL Steering Group for distribution on the 16th October 2019 with a deadline of 29th November, followed by a two-week extension until 13th December 2019 to assist with institutional scheduling. It was distributed by library and research offices through targeted emails to researchers, students and staff (as appropriate for each institution). Over this two-month period, the survey received 848 responses.

DATA NORMALISATION

The results of the survey were exported in Microsoft Excel format from Microsoft Forms. Data wrangling was required due to the format in which the responses were stored. Sub-datasets were created to split the results of the multiple-choice questions which were expressed together in single cells, and to restructure APC payment values which were captured in separate columns, while maintaining links to the institutional affiliation and the respondent ID number (for data validation purposes).

Outliers were identified in answers to the question ‘How much (in Euro) was paid for the APCs of your most recent articles?’ and seven submissions were deemed to be implausible based on comparison with the data provided to the OpenAPC Project: €1, €1, €1, €1.20, €5, €5, €5, €18,000.⁶

Chart 1: Visualisation of Outlier Data

This report is based on analysis with the outliers removed.

Data normalisation was carried out on the free-text responses to the following questions:

- ‘For approximately how many articles have you paid article processing charges?’
- ‘What was the source(s) of these [APC] funds (check all that apply)?’
- ‘Within the last 3 years, when submitting to and/or publishing in a journal, have you paid fees, other than open access fees, for (check all that apply)?’
- ‘What sources of funds have you used to pay such [non-OA] charges? Please check all that apply.’

High-level categorisations were also applied to:

- ‘For approximately how many articles have you paid article processing charges?’
 - 1-5, 6-10 etc
- ‘What was the source(s) of these [APC] funds (check all that apply)?’
 - Institutional Funding: My lab; My co-authors’ lab ; A fund at my (or my co-authors’) library or research office ; My department

⁶ J.H. Aasheim et al., *Datasets on Fee-Based Open Access Publishing Across German Institutions*. Bielefeld University, accessed May 20, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4119/UNIBI/UB.2014.18>

- Personal Funds: My personal funds ; My co-author’s personal funds⁷
- External Funding: Research funder/granting agency
- ‘What sources of funds have you used to pay such [non-OA] charges? Please check all that apply’.
 - As above.

Specific changes are detailed in Appendix 2.

FINDINGS

The survey received 848 responses from Dublin City University, Maynooth University, National University of Ireland Galway, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, Trinity College Dublin, TU Dublin City Campus (formerly Dublin Institute of Technology), University College Cork, University College Dublin and University of Limerick. The overall response rate is unknown as distribution audiences were controlled at the institution level. 12 respondents choose not to consent to the use of their data as stated in the ethical and GDPR statement and were not presented with the following questions.

Chart 2: Number of Respondents

The largest number of participants were from Trinity College Dublin (157), University College Dublin (143) and Dublin City University (140) who comprised roughly half of the respondents to the survey, followed by

⁷ It is acknowledged that ‘personal funds’ may have been interpreted by respondents as meaning their discretionary or personal research funds at their institutions. Due to the structure of the survey and that the ‘personal funds’ options were the only options given to participants to indicate that they paid from their own pockets and not from funds supported by their institution or grant, these sources have been categorised as personal rather than institutional or external.

the National University of Ireland Galway (121), University of Limerick (109), Maynooth University (82), University College Cork (56), Royal College of Surgeons (22) and TU Dublin City Campus (6).

Chart 3: Institutional Affiliation

Of the survey respondents, 62% (521) published open access journal articles. As IReL negotiates with publishers, seeking to enable 100% of our members' accepted articles to be published OA, it is encouraging to receive reports of robust OA publishing practices amongst respondents.

Chart 4: Open Access Publishing

Of those who published OA, 69% (361) of the respondents or their co-authors paid APCs. It is noteworthy the remaining 31% (160) of IReL authors have published diamond or platinum open access without APCs. This opens further research avenues, not covered by this survey, to investigate which journals IReL authors are choosing to publish in and how this contextualises IReL’s publisher agreements within the wider publishing landscape. The detailed IReL publication dataset, as referred to above, should address this question.

Chart 5: APC Payments

84% (299) of those who published open access journal articles, paid APCs for between 1 and 5 articles. These figures were distributed as follows: 28% (83) paid APCs for one article, 23% (69) paid APCs for 2 articles, 19% (56) paid APCs for 3 articles, 11% (35) paid APCs for 4 articles and 19% (56) paid APCs for 5 articles. Most participants in this survey have published a small amount of OA articles that required APCs. Of particular note in this dataset are the outliers, where the respondent stated that they paid for more than 40, more than 50 and more than 70 OA articles. Delving into the dataset further, the latter author stated ‘almost all of my papers are open access (>70)’ and indicated that APCs were paid ‘for every single one of them’. Of the authors that reporting paying for 20 or more articles (14), three utilised personal funds to assist in the payment or part-payment of APCs with the rest being covered by institutional or research funding. This demonstrates that prolific authors are largely being supported in their OA publishing and

provides a baseline for IReL's OA negotiations to ensure that support is maintained while reducing administrative burdens and streamlining efficiencies for the authors.

Chart 6: Number of APC-Paid OA Articles per Respondent (Detailed)

Chart 7: Number of 1-5 APC-Paid OA Articles per Respondent

In total, €1,373,588.11 in APCs were reported by the survey participants for their last three OA articles.

Payments from Trinity College Dublin and National University of Ireland Galway comprise nearly half of those reported, totalling €673,312.60 (€361,213.20 and €312,110.40 from 76 and 73 authors, respectively). Worthy of note is that Trinity College Dublin authors reported €49,102.80 more in APCs with only 3 more respondents. As figures derive from authors' last three articles and therefore don't relate to publishing frequency, differences may correlate to all authors' choice of journal (some have higher APCs than others) or perhaps suggests institutional-level preferences for more expensive hybrid over gold publishing (see OpenAPC data⁸).

Chart 8: Total APCs Reported by Institution

Further detail was captured, looking at the total expenditure by respondent for their last three articles, which averaged €4,004.63 per respondent. Extreme cases can be seen from the graph below, demonstrating some authors have paid in total between €11,800 and €13,500 for their last three articles.

⁸ Aasheim, *Datasets*

These data help us to understand the financial implications that OA has on individual researchers and the importance of IReL’s delivery of OA agreements that minimise the associated financial burden for authors.

Chart 9: Average APC Expenditure (3 Articles) by Respondent

Broken down to an APC cost per article, the survey captured that the average cost amongst those paid by the respondents was €1,765.54. By institution, the average single APC price paid per respondent was reported as follows:

Trinity College Dublin	€2,017.95
Royal College of Surgeons	€1,792.23
National University of Ireland, Galway	€1,763.34
University of Limerick	€1,748.96
University College Cork	€1,703.29
TU Dublin City Campus	€1,646.25
University College Dublin	€1,622.52
Maynooth University	€1,582.00
Dublin City University	€1,522.04

Table 1: Average APC Cost-Per-Article at Each Institution

These average APC figures demonstrate what IReL authors have been willing to pay to date and will be a valuable data point to benchmark publishers offers against IReL members' authors' expectations of current market value.

Chart 10: Average Cost Per Article by Respondent

Of primary importance to this survey is the data captured on the sources of funding for APCs. Authors stated that of all the sources used to pay for APCs (and multiple sources may have been used for individual APCs), personal funds were used 20% of the time. In the move to OA, there is **no expectation** that researchers should use personal funds to pay for publishing. As stated in the Plan S Principle 04: ‘Open Access publication fees are covered by the Funders or research institutions, not by individual researchers’.⁹ These figures demonstrate that a significant proportion of authors are paying for OA personally and highlights the urgent need for IReL to establish OA publishing agreements.

Broken down by institution, personal funds were used as follows:

University of Limerick	26%
University College Cork	25%
University College Dublin	24%
Royal College of Surgeons	23%
TU Dublin City Campus	20%

⁹ “Accelerating the Transition to Full and Immediate Open Access to Scientific Publications,” cOAlition S, accessed May 20, 2020, https://www.coalition-s.org/wp-content/uploads/PlanS_Principles_and_Implementation_310519.pdf

Dublin City University	19%
Maynooth University	18%
National University of Ireland, Galway	16%
Trinity College Dublin	14%

Table 2: Percentage of Personal Funds Used as Sources to Fund APCs at Each Institution

Of note in these figures is that Trinity College Dublin and National University of Ireland, Galway report the largest spending in APCs (see Chart 8), while authors in these institutions pay the least from their own personal funds. This demonstrates that authors at these institutions have the highest levels of institutional and grant/external funding to support their OA publishing.

In total, 36% of APCs reported in the survey used external funding. (This is a conservative figure, as funding from labs has been categorised for this study as being from institutional funds when they may, in practice, be grant-funded lab projects.) Going forward, authors that previously used grant funding to publish may instead be directed to IReL-funded publishing workflows, with eligibility to publish OA tied to their affiliation with IReL member institutions. Therefore, these figures demonstrate a need for a high-level re-evaluation of the funding landscape to ensure financial viability of IReL.

Chart 11: APC Funding Sources

Chart 12: APC Funding Sources (Categorised)

To contextualise APC payments, this survey also asked participants to report on payments of non-OA publication charges and their sources. Participants reported 243 instances of having paid for article submission, page charges, colour charges, image rights charges, reprints, cover art, overlength charges, supplementary material fees, video abstract fee, permission fees and proofreading fees in the last three years.

Chart 13: Non-OA Publication Charges

Respondents reported sources of payment for non-OA publication charges as 24% from personal funds, 28% from external funding, and 33% from institutional funding. This demonstrates that the funding landscape is relatively consistent, regardless of the type of publication charge (OA or non-OA). It also demonstrates that

publishers have set the precedent of publication charges; a practice that has now been adapted to include APCs.

Chart 14: Funding Sources for Non-OA Publication Charges (Categorised)

Chart 15: Funding Sources for Non-OA Publication Charges (Detailed)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Analysis of the survey results can facilitate some significant conclusions concerning authors in IReL member institutions:

1. They have published OA and have paid APCs to do so.
2. 20% have paid APCs from their own personal funds.
3. 24% have paid non-OA charges from their own personal funds.
4. 36% have paid APCs from external grant funding.
5. The average APC paid by respondents was €1,765.54.

The survey can only be taken to represent the respondents and not the community as a whole. However, with a large response of 848, confident assertions can be made that the proportions are representative.

This survey and resulting report highlight the opportunity for further research on the following topics:

- Number of APC payments on an annual basis
- Number of APC payments by publisher
- Number of OA articles published under OA agreements

Such further research will be particularly be useful as the number of OA agreements scales, enabling IReL to benchmark the impact of OA deals against current practices and drive improved outcomes for authors in OA agreement negotiations.

Note: the ‘Pay It Forward’ project sought to establish ‘whether a large-scale conversion to open access scholarly journal publishing funded via APCs would be viable and financially sustainable for this class of large North American research -intensive institutions’.¹⁰ It was not the aim of this IReL research or survey to do the same, but rather to provide initial data points to inform OA negotiations with publishers.

APPENDIX 1 | SURVEY TEXT

IReL Survey: Article Processing Charges

The Irish Research eLibrary (IReL), is a nationally funded online research library, providing access to quality peer-reviewed online research publications for member institutions. To ensure that IReL continues to offer

¹⁰ University of California Libraries, *Pay It Forward*, 10

excellent services and value for money in the provision of research e-resources on a sustainable basis, a survey is being carried out to assist in publisher negotiations in the context of open access.

Open access is a form of publishing that allows unrestricted access to peer-reviewed scholarly research. Within this model, publishers may be compensated for their efforts by the author(s) or his/her institution(s) at the point of publication rather than charging subscription fees for access to their journals.

An article processing charge (APC) is the fee that is typically paid by or on behalf of the author(s) to publish open access journal articles.

The survey is open until Friday 13th December 2019.

Ethical and GDPR Statement

Your participation in this research is voluntary and you are free to withdraw from the survey at any time.

The IReL office is located in Maynooth University (MU) and therefore data will be processed and stored in compliance with MU data protection policies. Anonymised data will be incorporated into IReL reporting for future strategic planning and may also feed into future reporting and publications on IReL activities to illustrate issues and points.

This survey is based on the University of California 'Pay It Forward' Report author survey:

https://www.library.ucdavis.edu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/ICIS-UC-Pay-It-Forward-Final-Report.rev_7.18.16.pdf. If you have any questions about the survey or procedures, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris, IReL Open Scholarship Officer (catherine.ferris@mu.ie).

1. *Do you consent to your data being used in the ways described above? Y/N*
2. *What is your home institution?*
 - Dublin City University
 - Maynooth University
 - National University of Ireland, Galway
 - Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
 - Trinity College Dublin
 - TU Dublin, City Campus
 - University College Cork
 - University College Dublin
 - University of Limerick

3. Have you ever published an open access journal article? Y/N
[If No Is Selected, Then Skip To [10]]

4. Have you or your co-authors paid article processing charges (either directly or through your institution, grant, or other funds) for any of the open access articles you have published? Y/N
[If No Is Selected, Then Skip To [10]]

5. For approximately how many articles have you paid article processing charges?

6. *[Answer If 5 Text Response Is Greater Than/Equal to 1]:* We would now like to ask about your most recent article(s) for which you paid APCs. If you have indicated that you have paid APCs for more than three articles, we will only ask you about the most recent three.

How much (in Euro) was paid for the APCs of your most recent articles?

Article 1 _____

7. How much (in Euro) was paid for the APCs of your most recent articles?

Article 2 _____

8. How much (in Euro) was paid for the APCs of your most recent articles?

Article 3 _____

9. What was the source(s) of these funds (check all that apply)?
 - My personal funds
 - My lab
 - My co-author's personal funds
 - My co-authors' lab
 - Research funder/granting agency
 - A fund at my (or my co-authors') library or research office
 - My department
 - Don't recall/not sure
 - Other (please specify) _____

10. Within the last 3 years, when submitting to and/or publishing in a journal, have you paid fees, other than open access fees, for (check all that apply):

- None
- Submission
- Colour charges
- Reprints
- Image rights
- Page charges
- Other (please specify) _____

11. What sources of funds have you used to pay such charges? Please check all that apply:

- My personal funds
- My lab
- My co-author's personal funds
- My co-authors' lab
- Research funder/granting agency
- A fund at my (or my co-authors') library or research office
- My department
- Don't recall/not sure
- Other (please specify) _____

APPENDIX 2: DATA NORMALISATION

For approximately how many articles have you paid article processing charges?		
<i>Original</i>	<i>Normalised</i>	<i>Categorised</i>
>20	21	21 – 25
10+	11	11 – 16
More than 10	11	11 – 16
5+	6	6 – 10
>20	21	21 – 25
20+ over a approx. 10 years period; coauthor institutions pay have paid the APC	21	21 – 25
more than 10	11	11 – 16

>10	11	11 – 16
50+	51	51 – 55
almost all of my papers are open access (>70) and I had to pay the open access fee for every single one of them	71	71 – 75
6+	7	6 – 10
i haven't paid myself. My co-authors have paid for 3 papers. We got one free from Royal Society	3	1 – 5
over 15	16	16 – 20
more than 5	6	6 – 10
10 or more	10	6 – 10
more than 5	6	6 – 10
>40	41	41 – 45
Dozens	24	21 – 25
6 or more	6	6 – 10
~20	20	16 – 20
What was the source(s) of these [APC] funds (check all that apply)?		
<i>Original</i>	<i>Normalised</i>	<i>Categorised</i>
OBRSS; please note that a 50% discount was received for one of the APCs (€595);	A fund at my (or my co-authors') library or research office	Institutional Funding
From consultancy funding;	Other	External Funding
Some personal (€500) and some research committee DCU (€1500);	My personal funds A fund at my (or my co-authors') library or research office	Personal Funds ; Institutional Funds
industry collaborator's company paid one;	Other	External Funding

My overhead allocation;	Research funder/granting agency	External Funding
My own research account;	Research funder/granting agency	External Funding
My co-author works in Queen's University Belfast and the Institution pay a fee each year to BMC to publish in their journals. This covers all articles whereby a staff member is the corresponding author on the paper. ;	Other	Other
H2020 insisted on, but paid out of PI account;	Research funder/granting agency	External Funding
I received a personal grant ;	Other	External Funding
Sometimes supplemented with MDPI vouchers;	Other	Other
I had a slush fund at my previous university that covered a range of research costs. I used it.;	A fund at my (or my co-authors') library or research office	Institutional Funding
Overhead from an industrially-funded project;	Other	External Funding
Within the last 3 years, when submitting to and/or publishing in a journal, have you paid fees, other than open access fees, for (check all that apply)		
<i>Original</i>	<i>Normalised</i>	
does not apply (have not submitted);	blank	
Not published;	blank	
I'm not published;	blank	
Haven't published yet;	blank	
None;Submission;	Submission	

None;Reprints;Page charges;	Reprints Page Charges	
None;Page charges;	Page charges	
New to research - yet to publish;	blank	
None;Submission;	Submission	
None;Page charges;	Page charges	
None;Colour charges;	Colour charges	
Article processing charges;Page charges;	Page charges	
What sources of funds have you used to pay such [non-OA] charges? Please check all that apply		
<i>Original</i>	<i>Normalised</i>	<i>Categorised</i>
N/A;	blank	
Never paid;	blank	
UCD OBRSS;	A fund at my (or my co-authors') library or research office	Institutional Funds
APC's are neither common nor necessary in my field of mathematics. There are good quality open-access journals with no author charges; this should be the model pursued in future. ;	blank	
None;	blank	
Haven't paid such charges as I would not have access to funds other than my personal funds so this has deterred me from publishing in these journals requesting payment of fees;	blank	
Didnt pay any fees as I didnt submit to an open access journal;	blank	
NA, but it would be through personal funds as there isn't much support for this.;	blank	

I have not paid any fees - I/my department have no funding so I always seek out journals that don't charge an author fee;	blank	
Not relevant. I haven't paid fees;	blank	
have not paid;	blank	
Not Relevant;	blank	
did not pay;	blank	
I would NEVER pay to have an article published in a journal, open access or not. This is a travesty. ;	blank	
Don't pay to publish;	blank	
did not have to pay fees;	blank	
sfi research center;	Research funder/granting agency	External Funding
There are currently no designated sources for such funding at TCD. It would be unreasonable to expect me to pay for them myself.;	blank	
It is a principle not to use pay option;	blank	
I dont have money for it and so have not published in open access;	blank	
Choose non OA publications;My personal funds;	My personal funds	Personal Funds
Research project account ;	Research funder/granting agency	External Funding
Overheads;	Research funder/granting agency	External Funding
Not applicable (don't pay APCs);	blank	
I don't have any funds available - ;	blank	